

THE DEVELOPMENT OF A SOCIAL-MEDIA-STRATEGY FOR THE OPEN SEARCH FOUNDATION APPLYING THE SOCIAL-MEDIA-CYCLE

A. J. Decker, Technical University Ingolstadt, Ingolstadt , Germany and
Open Search Foundation, Starnberg, Germany

Abstract

On the Second Open Search Symposium in 2020 the foundations for a tailor-made OSF communication approach were presented [1]. As demonstrated, for an unknown Non-profit organization (NPO) like the OSF the necessary focal points in the beginning of the communication approach must be the set-up of awareness and attention for the existing monopoly-problem in the search market as well as the building of a group of supporters. Due to the fact, that the OSF still lacks the necessary funding to run big campaigns, alternative ways must be found. In this context, Social Media plays a big role, because major steps can be taken towards the goals described without big investments in terms of money. A solution can be provided, that can be executed with the help of the existing volunteer members.

Talking about Social Media, one thing can unfortunately still be observed in corporate practice today: there is a lack of competence in developing Social Media strategies. Michelle Charello [2], author of the American textbook "Essentials of Social Media Marketing" summarizes the situation in the market as follows: „Too many businesses struggle with social media because they lack a well defined social media strategy.”

As a consequence, particularly an NPO like the OSF should not start the adventure Social Media without such a well defined Social Media strategy. Just like Warren Buffet said: “It takes 20 years to build a reputation and five minutes to ruin it.” This is true for all companies, but it is especially true for an NPO that pursues charitable goals.

Hence, the first step in Social Media for the OSF must be the profound development of a Social Media strategy. In order to do so, a project at the Technical University of Ingolstadt from March until June 2021 with 26 master students of the Marketing / Sales / Media program was set up under the coordination of Professor Alexander Decker. As the basic framework to develop such a Social Media strategy the so called Social-Media-Cycle [5] was used. This ten-step approach guides companies systematically through all the necessary strategic and operative steps. Out of the ten steps of the Social-Media-Cycle, six were executed in the project:

- Step 1: Social Media monitoring: all relevant social media platforms were observed with regard to mentions of the OSF and the most important alternative search engines.

- Step 2: Definition of objectives per target groups: Based on the findings of the monitoring and the objectives and target groups of the general OSF communication approach, nine target groups were identified and further described in detail (including the objectives), focussing on both, people we need to address with regard to the awareness problem, and those we want to gain as supporters.
- Step 3: Selection of the focus platforms used by the OSF: The target groups identified with their respecting objectives led to the selection of three platforms: LinkedIn and Twitter to start with. Instagram to follow later on.
- Step 4: Organisational aspects: Due to the lack of resources, organisational aspects had to be taken into consideration as well. Particularly, a social media integration model (following the well-known Altimeter approach) had to be chosen and the roles of the Social Media team had to be defined.
- Step 5: Iteration: All information from step 1 to 4 were put together and iterated in order to come up with a first Social Media strategy approach. This resulted in a Social Media architecture, that encompasses the final seven (out of nine) target groups, the objectives to be achieved, the channels chosen for them and first indications of the content to be produced in step 7.
- Step 7: Content calendar: A content calendar for the three chosen platforms was developed with ideas and first posts as well as a set of five explanation videos.

Due to the fact that the project is still ongoing and the final strategy has yet to be approved by the OSF board, the operative steps 6 and 8 to 10 could not be implemented so far.

The presentation will show the major outcomes of the project and the strategy developed in more detail.

REFERENCES

- [1] Decker, A. / Hiemer, C. (2020): Beyond Tech: Rising Awareness for the Open Search Foundation through a Tailor-Made Communication Approach. *Proceedings for the 2. International Symposium on Open Search, CERN, Geneva, Switzerland. Electronically published via:* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4593332>.
- [2] Charello M (2020): Essentials of Social Media Marketing. The Most Up-to-date Social Media Marketing E-textbook. *Stukent, Idaho Falls.*
- [3] Decker, A. (2019) Der Social-Media-Zyklus. *Springer-Gabler, Wiesbaden.*